

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Interdisciplinary Synergy in Practice: Learning Outcomes, Success, and Challenges of open-ended interdisciplinary Design-Science collaborations

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Guidelines scientific journal

The *Journal of Science Communication* (JCOM) is a journal that publishes articles in the realm of science communication. Its published articles are open-access without the charge of a fee. This journal was chosen due to its broad range of science communication issues, including scholars from sociology, science and technology studies, media and communication, museum studies and other disciplinary perspectives. Thus, JCOM encourages interdisciplinary exchange and research which applies to this research project (*About JCOM*, n.d.).

The journal guidelines, which have been applied to this research are as follows:

Articles (i.e., research articles) present new empirical research using quantitative and/or qualitative methods. Your research article should be supported by a comprehensive literature review, a thorough theoretical grounding, enough detail within the methodology section to orient readers to how the authors plan to address the aims of the study, strong and original findings, and a conclusion with implications for the research and practice communities. Research articles are peer-reviewed. Your manuscript should be 5,000 – 8,000 words long, including an abstract of 100 – 150 words and literature references. JCOM uses APA citation and reference list style (Guidelines for Authors, n.d.).

Abstract

Interdisciplinary Art-Science collaborations exceed the boundaries of a single discipline to explore, learn, and create together. However, little focus lies on the internal processes of collaborations and how they impact the participants. Thus, in this study, I explore the learning outcomes, success, and challenges through the qualitative analysis of six semi-structured interviews with participants of the project *Collaborations for Future*. Results revealed cognitive, normative, and relational social learning outcomes gained through the collaborative process that remained six months after the end of the project. Besides that, all participants maintained the collaboration beyond the timeline as they attribute individual and collective growth and a tangible outcome as valuable. Nevertheless, institutional structures lack support for interdisciplinary encounters as regulations hinder providing resources equally and foster long-term investigation. Thus, this study points out the need for research and funding structures beyond disciplines and timelines to create an environment for interdisciplinary synergy.

Introduction

Interdisciplinary collaborations show a high potential for addressing and grasping complex, multi-faced problems of our time (Klein, 1990). As coordinated relationships between disciplines, interdisciplinary collaborations exceed the disciplinary boundaries of one realm and foster a joint exploration to reach a shared goal (Popa et al., 2015; Schnugg, 2019). In this way, the expertise and methodologies of different disciplines are combined to jointly explore and express societal issues, and sustainability challenges, and create space for disciplines to expand their knowledge (Bieluch et al., 2017; Trott et al., 2020). Thus, interdisciplinary practices often facilitate an exchange, novel, and critical understanding and communication of complex social, ecological, cultural, and economic challenges (Clark et al., 2020).

This is especially the case, “regarding the fact that collective action and behavioral change, at all scales, is strongly dependent on networks and flows of information between individuals and groups [...]” (Paterson et al., 2020). Edwards (2010) describes the flow of information and even the fusion of methods between art and science that results in an outcome beyond the conventional boundaries of each discipline as Art-Science. As such a joint exploration of artists and scientists, Art-Science shows valuable contributions to a sustainable society (Galafassi et al., 2018; Gibbs, 2014; Kagan, 2014). In this study, art refers to “modes of expression [...] that use skill or imagination for in the creation of aesthetic objects, environments, or experiences that can be shared with others“, including design as a practice of art (Trott et al., 2020). Besides its aesthetic and communicative functions, the inherent inquiry of art is of importance (Robbins, 2022). Halpern & Rogers (2021) categorize Art-science collaborative practices and their values into four types: (a) conveyance of a message, (b) generation of knowledge, (c) contextualizing of science, and (d) posing critique about scientific practices.

Besides that, interdisciplinary collaborations also impact the participants. Social learning is considered an important aspect of Art-Science collaborations (Herrero et al., 2019; Westberg & Polk, 2016). Social learning refers to learning processes initiated and fostered through social interaction which allows for modification of the vision, perspectives, and assumptions on the collaborative topic (Hadorn et al., 2008; Popa et al., 2015). Baird et al. (2014) distinguish cognitive, normative, and relational learning as social learning outcomes of interactive decision-making processes for climate change adaption. Cognitive learning includes expanding or restructuring knowledge. Normative learning is defined as learning on an emotional level including reflection processes and shifts in values or perspectives. Relational learning refers to qualities participants use or rely on when interacting, for instance, the ability

of open communication (Baird et al., 2014). Gallois et al. (2024) made use of the concept for their research on Art-Science collaborations during the European Performing Science Night 2021. The results showed social learning processes such as the exchange of practices, knowledge, and perspectives of the researched Art-Science collaborations (Gallois et al., 2024). These individual learning outcomes help to link back to societal needs and impacts (Paterson et al., 2020).

Despite challenging and overcoming discipline-based linear thinking through collaboration, collaborations also raise new challenges (Gibbs, 2014; Heras et al., 2021). These barriers can be internal or external. Participants in Art-Science collaboration reported internal challenges related to roles and team dynamics, or emotional tensions from experiencing stress, discomfort, or frustration to motivation, excitement, or confidence (Gallois et al., 2024; Gibbs, 2014; Heras et al., 2021). External barriers comprise facilitation considerations, processes, and structures. Nevertheless, due to the guidance through facilitators, internal and external factors are closely linked. Facing these barriers through facilitating a sustainable collaboration is a complex process that is often novel and unestablished in institutions (Bieluch et al., 2017; Schnugg & Song, 2020). Often, Art-Science collaborations rely on a person responsible within an institution who identifies the value of such collaborations (Schnugg & Song, 2020). Thus, the establishment of Art-Science collaborations remains challenging. Setting up and realizing a successful Art-Science collaboration requires detailed planning, curation, and facilitation (Schnugg & Song, 2020).

The foundation *Foundation We Are* sets up, creates, and facilitates such space for designers and scientists to connect and collaborate. Their project *Collaborations for Future* is a local example in the Netherlands for such an Art-Science project addressing the ecological challenges of our time (*Programme - Collaborations for Future*, 2025). For nine months, ten designers and ten scientists, in pairs of 1-on-1, participated in an open-ended collaboration. The only predefined parameters were the partners, a time frame of nine months, the collective process, and the funding conditions. The outcome was an exhibition exploring the ten science-design collaborations on global and local climate challenges (Dimitrova & Szwaj, 2024). Accompanying research during the projects' timeline indicated learning outcomes on the individual level. For instance, the participants highlighted that they had accessed new places, both physically and conceptually, and developed new ways of thinking and working (Dimitrova & Szwaj, 2024).

However, impact assessments are often conducted within the timeframe of the Art-Science collaboration and lack the perspective on long-term impacts on participants (Clark et al., 2020;

Gallois et al., 2024; Gibbs, 2014). Long-term measurements of interdisciplinary collaborations on social transformation and the individual level remain challenging (Schnugg & Song, 2020; Paterson et al., 2020) Conventional qualitative evaluation measures are often limited to disciplinary value structures and thus can not capture the value of interdisciplinary collaborative processes (Paterson et al., 2020). Besides that, evaluation after the termination of a collaborative project is also hindered due to the founding stop after the end of the project¹. Thus, there is a need to investigate the long-term effect of design science collaborations on participants after the termination of the collaboration (Paterson et al., 2020; Schnugg & Song, 2020).

This research builds on findings on the learning, challenges, and values of Art-Science collaborations and investigates these aspects in the case of the interdisciplinary Design-Science project *Collaborations for Future*. It explores the social learning outcomes during the collaboration as well as its relation to the long-term impact on participants. In addition, it captures challenges participants faced during and after the collaboration and gives insights into the participants' perspective on a successful Design-Science collaboration. Through interviews, six months after termination of the project this study adds a temporal dimension to the research of interdisciplinary Art-Science collaborations. As such, it is a follow-up study on the *Collaborations For Future* half a year after the end of the collaboration between the scientist and the designer investigating the research question:

What are the social learning and post-collaboration outcomes, values, and challenges of the interdisciplinary Design-Science project Collaborations for Future beyond the project's timeline?

¹ Meeting with Alexandra Sz waj, online, 19.02.2025

Methods

Participants and data collection

This study employs interviews as a method to collect data (Clark et al., 2020; Gallois et al., 2024). To answer the posed research question, six interviews with participants of the project *Collaborations For Future* were conducted and subsequently analyzed. All interviewees contributed to the collaboration as participants in one of the collaborative teams that consisted of two people in total, one climate scientist and one designer. During the process of collaboration, all scientists were doing a PhD. The research of the interviewed scientists comprises projects aiming to provide sustainable future transitions, capture climate impacts on ecosystems, and track the societal dimensions of climate policy. The work of designers comprised fields of architecture, interdisciplinary design and research, and speculative design. Interviewees were chosen regarding their early stage in their career as a PhD student, a diverse depiction of collaboration types, and the availability of both parties of a collaboration (Dimitrova & Sz waj, 2024). For more detailed information about the interviewees and the projects see Dimitrova & Sz waj (2024). The interviews are used to gain an understanding of the participants' personal experiences towards interdisciplinary collaborations. For this, the chosen semi-structured interview approach encouraged the interviewees to reconstruct their experiences and created the possibility for narrative depth (Croucher & Cronn-Mills, 2021b; Seidman, 2006). The interview guide comprised eight questions. The questions followed a thematic order of (1) the participants' general experience and social learning outcomes, (2) post-collaboration outcomes, and (3) the participants' perspective on the value of interdisciplinary collaborations. The interview guide is provided in Appendix Table 3.

The author of this research, Sophie Straetemans conducted the interviews online. The interviews were recorded with the prior consent of the participant. Subsequently, the data gathered was prepared by transcribing the record to analyze the data in the following. The interview transcripts are provided on request.

Before the interview, ethical considerations were approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Science of Leiden University. In addition, interviewees filled in information about the informed consent following the ethics requirements². The ethical considerations and decisions about the project can be found in Appendix Table 4. The participant's personal data was anonymized and coded according to the occupation of the participant: S/DNumgr with D =

² <https://www.staff.universiteitleiden.nl/security/information-security-and-privacy/privacy-and-gdpr/informed-consent/service-units/ict-shared-service-centre?cf=service-units&cd=ict-shared-service-centre>

Designer, S = Scientist; Numgr = participants' group number. The personal data can only be accessed by the researcher and the supervisors.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the interviews was analyzed using a qualitative content analysis. This research aims to capture new insights from participants' experiences in interdisciplinary collaborations. Thus, the chosen qualitative analysis is the conventional method which uses an inductive approach (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). The coding technique applied to the interview transcripts is axial coding. The coding framework developed from the coding process and guided the classification of the data into categories and themes (Croucher & Cronn-Mills, 2021a). Nevertheless, the coding process was guided by results (Baird et al., 2014; Gallois et al., 2024) and frameworks (Schauppenlehner-Kloyber & Penker, 2015) on social learning outcomes in collaborative projects. Participants' answers on social learning outcomes were categorized according to their cognitive, normative, and or relational learning (Baird et al., 2014). In addition, post-collaboration outcomes, participants' perspectives on success and challenges which could not be categorized as social learning outcomes were coded separately. The codebook can be found in Appendix Table 5.

Inter-coder reliability above 75 percent was reached after adjustments of the codebook according to the feedback of the second coder and the second time testing the inter-coder reliability (Neuendorf, 2017; Popping, 1988). The interview transcripts were coded using the software Atlas.ti Web. In addition, the codebook, coded quotations, and results are captured in an Excel file (Supplementary Data) using Microsoft Excel Version 16.77 and graphs are visualized using RStudio Version 2023.06.2+561.

Results

In the conducted interviews, participants of the project *Collaborations for Future* reported learning outcomes, their perception of the success of interdisciplinary Design-Science collaborations, and challenges they have experienced. The learning outcomes are separated into social learning outcomes, which were developed or deepened during the collaboration, and additional post-collaboration outcomes, which apply to the period after termination of the project.

Perceived social learning outcomes

The project *Collaborations for Future* resulted in the development or deepening of the three distinct social learning outcomes defined cognitive learning, normative learning, and relational learning. In total, the social learning outcomes scored the highest number of counts over all interviews with a total of 62 times mentioned (Figure 1). Comparing this to the count of themes (Figure 2), a similar pattern can be observed. Here, every code counts once per interviewee. All learning outcomes were mentioned by every scientist and designer, except the normative learning which was mentioned by all designers and two scientists (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1 The total count of codes mentioned in interviews; The y-axis shows the total number of counts in the interview transcripts. The x-axis shows the Codes that refer to the themes. The colors indicate the theme of Social

learning outcome in blue, Post-collaboration outcome in green, Success of Design-Science collaborations in yellow, and Challenges in orange.

Figure 2 The codes mentioned per interviewee; The y-axis shows the mentioning of a theme per interviewee as counts in the interview transcripts. The x-axis shows the Codes that refer to the themes. The colors indicate the affiliation to either the designer in light blue or the scientist in dark blue. The link to the overarching themes: Social learning outcome: Cognitive learning, Normative learning, Relational learning; Post-collaboration outcome: Continuation of collaboration, Future work, and collaborations, Success of Design-Science collaborations: Communication & Outreach, Sustainability & Long-term engagement, Collaboration dynamics, Individual growth, Challenges: Engagement & Team dynamics, Maintenance and Sustainability, Facilitation, Impact, Understanding.

Referring to Cognitive learning, the project allowed participants to explore and access topics from another angle. One designer describes their cognitive learning process as “witness[ing] and absorb[ing] the whole scientific method” (D2). Through the collaboration they gained new perspectives and possibilities, often introduced through the understanding of disciplines and or the extension of the network. In some cases, these new cognitive learning outcomes resulted in the extension of their professional approaches, as shown in the following quote: *“[...] For me, this was really like an experience [...] that I was actually looking for in my PhD trajectory. So, in general, I must say it [...] opened up a lot of possibilities and doors for me in that regard, [...] not necessarily in the practical [...] but in my own head as well.”* (S1).

This perception is also shared by another scientist (S3) who at the beginning of the project just started her PhD. Thus, she reported that the concurrent timelines and interaction with the designer helped her to *“think about [her] own topic also [in] a very different way”* (S3).

Similarly, the participants also experienced normative learning outcomes on an emotional level. Through the collaboration, both scientists and designers reflected on their occupations and roles within the collaboration. In this reflective process, participants experience a change of perception or a shift in values. One designer *“reflected on the methods [she has] been using in [her] practice and [methods she has] learned [in the collaboration]”* (D3). This process is induced through interaction with a person outside of their discipline. *“[They] got pulled out of [their] bubble”* (S2). This view from the outside helps the participant to place their own work into perspective, which in some cases also leads to new motivation:

“[My way of thinking] broadened. [...] It was rebrought into my perspective. [...] I was on this little narrow path. It had been naturally narrowing. [...] I sort of got [...] to keep everything that I learned on this narrow path and then broaden it again. She [her partner] kind of romanticized [my scientific work] again for me. Because I love what I do and I am doing it because I love it. But it also [...] becomes so normalized.” (S2).

Besides that, the designers and scientists mentioned relational competencies as skills they have learned through the social collaborative process of the project. They refer to the collaboration as an opportunity to *“combine or join forces”* and *“create something new out of that”* (S1). Participants also highlighted the importance of applying an open approach with open communication, for instance *“[speaking] transparently about the expectations”* (S1). This approach led to an equal involvement of both parties, for one scientist despite her expectation *“to be less involved”* (S2). Instead, the pairs of scientists and designers merged their abilities like a *“Venn diagram of [their] work and [their] interests [which] ended up lining up really well”* (S2). For both parties, this meant learning approaches that are not necessarily connected to their own profession, as mentioned in the following quote:

“For designers [...] we’re used to open-ended or ambiguous things. Scientists [...] need to know what [they are] working towards. [...] So for me it was actually more a way of testing how I’ve already collaborated and [...] taking more of a leadership role in the projects, whereas the collaboration itself was very equal” (D1).

Post-collaboration outcomes

Exceeding the acquisition of learning outcomes within the projects’ timeline, every pair reported the continuation of the collaboration or application of the collaboration’s outcome beyond the official timeline (Figure 2). The continuation comes in different shapes. For several collaborative pairs, the outcome is used as a science communication product within the

institute. “[D2’s] photos are used, will be used for years [...]. There’s a lot of interest from other scientists because we all want to communicate our work” (S2). For other collaborations, the relationship and network are actively maintained and collaborative experiences are shared through conferences (D1 and S1), lunch lectures (D3 and S3), or incorporating the partner into the think tank of a new project (D1 and S1). On a personal level, one designer also joins the upcoming field work and continues to capture the scientific process even without funding (D2 and S2).

Success of Design-Science Collaborations

Every participant considered their Design-Science collaboration as a success. Thereby, the participant’s perspective on the success of the collaboration was strongly characterized by the dynamic of the collaboration. Every interviewee mentioned the process of the collaboration including the team dynamics as justification for the final success (Table 1). For instance, one designer said *“I think for me a big part of like a successful design science collaboration is that you’re really interested and open in each other’s fields. That also means that you’re really open towards each other, so you kind of become really good friends. [...] For me, the emphasis lies on the process and learning from each other”* (D1). In addition, the importance of personal and professional individual growth to define the success of the collaboration was mentioned four times by participants (Table 1). S3 described the collaboration as valuable because her partner *“took [her] out of this very data focused modeling driven world where [she] only look[s] at [her] laptop to explore the real world”*. In comparison, S2 reflected on personal success: *“If we had not had the oversight of Foundation We Are or Collaboration for Future I think I would still consider it a personal success just because it was a great experience.”* Despite the personal experiences, three designers considered *“[...] reach[ing] a wide public”* (D2), *“tangibilize [...] for the public”* (D1), and creating a product for *“people to interact with it”* (D1) as a success.

Table 1 Codes of the theme “Success of Design-Science collaboration” which emerged from the interviews. Values that are being talked about in the results are marked in bold.

Theme	Success: Communication and outreach of the product	Success: Sustainability & Long-term engagement	Success: Collaboration dynamics	Success: Individual growth
n	3	1	6	4
n scientist	0	1	3	3
n designer	3	0	3	1

Challenges

Nevertheless, without targeting the challenges of Design-Science collaborations in the interviews by asking questions about it, five different codes emerged from the interviews (Figure 2 and Table 2). The most mentioned was the facilitation where participants experienced challenges due to the structure and support. Challenges faced by the facilitation of the project were perceived towards the intransparency of the foundations' guidance: *"I think they thought we had this idea too early in the process. So, they did push us away a bit from it [...]"* (D3). In addition, most facilitation challenges were directed toward the general challenge of providing a platform for different disciplines to collaborate *"[Participants of collaborations are] taking the initiative and that's so much extra work for people. So, I think that also holds back a lot [of people]."* (S2). Linked to the personal initiative needed to contribute to the collaboration, participants experienced this challenge affecting the engagement and team dynamics. In this project, the funding was attributed to the designers, and could not fund the scientists' work. *"[...] It can also make a difference in how important you think this is for you and how much time you want to contribute to this. [...] I see it as a part that can help me in my further career or my further development but I can also imagine that other scientists don't see this as a valuable collaboration for their career"* (S1). Every collaboration of the project resulted in an outcome at the end of the project's timeline. However, participants also reported, that despite getting guidance from the foundation on how to maintain the outcome, implementing or realizing that was challenging. In all collaborations, the termination of the project was the cause of this challenge which *"[...] made it] very hard to put that in practice when the funding stops"* (S1).

Table 2 Codes of the theme "Challenges" that emerged from the interviews. Values that are being talked about in the results are marked in bold.

Theme	Challenges: Engagement & Team Dynamics	Challenges: Maintenance & Sustainability	Challenges: Facilitation	Challenges: Impact	Challenges: Understanding
n	3	3	4	2	1
n scientist	2	1	2	1	0
n designer	1	2	2	1	1

Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, social and post-collaboration learning outcomes, and the participant's perspective on success and challenges of the interdisciplinary Design-Science project *Collaborations for Future* were investigated through qualitative interviews. Besides the continuation of the collaboration for all pairs as a post-collaboration outcome, social learning outcomes defined by Baird et al. (2014), namely cognitive, normative, and relational learning were identified for all participants. Resulting from the learning outcomes, every participant defined their collaboration as a successful experience justified with for instance the collaboration dynamic that shaped the learning processes. Nonetheless, participants also reported challenges arising from interdisciplinary collaborations and the structure supporting such projects which can influence collaboration dynamics and limit the impact the collaborations can have.

Social learning outcomes

Interdisciplinary practices often facilitate an exchange, novel, and critical understanding and communication of complex social, ecological, cultural, and economic challenges (Clark et al., 2020). However, Schnugg & Song (2020) highlight the difficulty of determining tangible outcomes of interdisciplinary Art-Science practices that manifest as a cause of the collaboration and that are measurable. Thus, this study focuses on the process of collaboration as a result of the collaboration which involves social learning instead of a tangible outcome. By facilitating this interdisciplinary collaboration *Foundation We Are* supported an open space for participants to develop or deepen competencies, support learning, and create relationships beyond the projects' timeline. In this study, all participants experienced social learning outcomes resulting from the collaborations. Participants reported for instance exploring new topics, gaining new perspectives, or possibilities, which we, according to Baird et al. (2014) defined as cognitive learning. Similarly, these cognitive impacts on participants are also reported in previous studies on Art-Science practices (Harris, 1999; Heras et al., 2021; Schnugg & Song, 2020). Gibbs (2014) describes cognitive learning as a process of learning beyond each discipline's learning opportunities by adopting new practices and gaining new insights. Interdisciplinary collaborations encourage new ways of thinking (Gallois et al., 2024; Schnugg & Song, 2020) which in this study for two scientists resulted in shaping their PhD trajectory at the beginning of their academic career.

Connected to cognitive learning, participants also experienced normative learning, learning on an emotional level (Baird et al., 2014). The collaboration with a partner outside of their discipline provided the opportunity to view the participants' work from an outsider's

perspective. For some participants, this resulted in reflection processes on their work, motivation, or even a shift in values. Gallois et al. (2024) investigated the learning processes of interdisciplinary collaborations between 28 artists and scientists during the European Performing Science Night 2021. In their study, they could also show the impact of the collaborations on the internal perceptions of the participants, such as the motivation (Gallois et al., 2024). Merging artistic and scientific practices or ideas can lead to sense-making or giving processes for participants (Schnugg & Song, 2020). This was also mentioned by one participant who experienced that her discipline got romanticised again after it became normalised throughout her academic career.

Due to the interactive nature of collaboration relational skills are crucial for a successful project since participants rely on those when collaborating (Steelman et al., 2019). Relational learnings mentioned in the literature include communication and network skills and learning about group dynamics (Gallois et al., 2024; Schnugg & Song, 2020; Steelman et al., 2019). As shown in Dowell & Weitkamp (2012) investigating the collaborative process of science-inspired theater, shared understanding was reached through relational skills, such as discussions, feedback questions, and exchange of ideas. In this study, learning collaborative skills enabled the collaboration partners to merge disciplines, work equally together on the project, and create a collective result, in one case despite the initial expectation of the scientist to be less involved.

Success and post-collaboration outcome

Social learning is considered an important aspect of Art-Science collaborations due to its process (Herrero et al., 2019; Westberg & Polk, 2016). As previously mentioned, besides tangible outcomes, personal learning outcomes are crucial and impact the participant and their perspective beyond the timeline of the project (Schnugg & Song, 2020). Gallois et al. (2024) showed that participation in interdisciplinary collaborations allowed participants to see the value in them. All scientists and designers of this study attributed value to the collaboration and its success based on the collaboration dynamics, the process of learning from each other. Supporting this observation Gallois et al. (2024) pointed power dynamics and inclusiveness out as a crucial aspect of engagement in collaboration. Hence, unequal group dynamics can also act as a possible barrier to individual participation. In contrast, creating an environment for balanced contribution and trust fosters individual participation and with that also the group dynamics. (Gallois et al., 2024). This was also observed in this study, where participants justified the success by equal team dynamics, individual growth, and the science communication and outreach of the collaboration. Nevertheless, artists and scientists put more

emphasis and importance on team dynamics and personal development than tangible outcomes. The justification of value and success through team dynamics and individual growth reconnects to the social learning outcomes. Intertwining individual and collective needs, Art-Science collaborations can be valuable to all contributing parties, not only the participants but also the facilitators, its network, and the disciplines included (Schnugg, 2019; Schnugg & Song, 2020).

As such values remain, this study aimed to investigate the impact of Design-Science collaborations on participants beyond the timeline. While, most studies (Dowell & Weitkamp, 2012; Gibbs, 2014; Paterson et al., 2020) focus on the timeframe of the project, this study tried to additionally capture long-term effects and outcomes that are not immediate tangible outcomes. By conducting interviews nine months after the termination of the project, perspectives on the continuation of the collaboration and perceptions on future collaborations are captured. The experience of the project strengthened the intersection of art and science (Gallois et al., 2024). Every partnership reported the continuation of the collaboration. The collaboration is maintained through a presentation at conferences or lunch lectures, incorporating the partner into future work, or using the outcome as a science communication product.

As science communication as a post-collaboration outcome remains, it has also been considered as a criterion for participants to define a successful and valuable collaboration. Similarly, participants in the study Lesen et al. (2016) also valued art as a tool for science communication. At the collaborative Art-Science collaboration *SiteWorks*, participants mentioned the idea of art as a tool to communicate science (Gibbs, 2014). Encountering climate challenges through collaborative work of the disciplines of art and science offers alternative means of communication. It can lower the entry threshold by providing diverse access points and create awareness by building different connections to science (Heras et al., 2021). However, art or design needs to be recognized as an equal contribution to the collaboration beyond a service-sub orientation of its communication skills (Halpern & Rogers, 2021; Robbins, 2022). An equal collaboration enables both disciplines to reflect, observe, and apply different approaches and thus creates a new space for exploration beyond each discipline's boundaries (Gibbs, 2014).

Challenges

Creating space for exploration beyond the disciplines' boundaries, however, was mentioned by all participants as a challenge of the Design-Science encounters. Specifically, the challenges pointed out in this study are the facilitation, team dynamics, and the maintenance

of the collaboration's outcome. In addition, participants explained these barriers to be intertwined. The funding aims to create space for interdisciplinary encounters. However, the financial support disbursed by the ministry and received by the foundation is counteractive, as it was only allowed to be allocated to the designers. Thus, scientists could not be compensated and contributed to the project based on the value they attribute to Design-Science collaborations. This creates restricted space and barriers for people willing to engage in interdisciplinary collaborations, but do not have the financial and temporal resources to contribute (Dowell & Weitkamp, 2012). Successful collaborative work requires the investment of both parties (Gibbs, 2014). Inequal funding can impact the participants by leading to unbalanced engagement and team dynamics. These imbalances are shown to reduce the potential of group learning (Schauppenlehner-Kloyber & Penker, 2015) and individual learning outcomes with transformative potential (Gallois et al., 2024; Popa et al., 2015). Additionally, imbalances might foster the unequal contribution, dominance of one discipline, and sub-orientation of the other discipline (Halpern & Rogers, 2021; Robbins, 2022). Dowell & Weitkamp (2012) showed the importance of 'Availability of funding' for participants of a science-inspired theater collaboration as a motivation for contribution. The lack of funding in general, but here especially equal funding limits Art-Science encounters to contributors who are already interested and attribute value for their personal development (Schnugg & Song, 2020). Subsequently, the power funders hold and the influence they have on shaping interdisciplinary projects is far-reaching. In addition, participants of this study explained despite receiving guidance from *Foundation We Are* on the maintenance of the collaborations' outcome the realization of it was challenging. Similar to the previous argument, the challenge of maintenance arose from the lack of resources. Nevertheless, sustainable contributions of collaborations are based on learning outcomes that remain (Strauß, 2018), but also on the possibility of continuation. Thus, institutional and financial support within and beyond the timeline of a project is an essential factor for the success and sustainability of Art-Science collaborations (Dowell & Weitkamp, 2012; Gibbs, 2014).

Conclusion

This research on the project *Collaborations for Future* showed that Design-Science collaborations provide a space to explore, learn, and create together beyond the boundaries of disciplines. Assessing the value of interdisciplinary encounters poses difficulties since approaches are not able to capture values beyond their disciplinary values. Thus, this research focuses on the perception of participants instead of conventional approaches, for instance, quantitative methods such as visitor numbers. The perception of the participants six months after the project ended revealed social learning outcomes and the continuation of projects as an essential value for participants. Nevertheless, there is a lack of long-term studies tracking

the impact of interdisciplinary collaborations beyond its timeline. This might be due to institutional barriers not providing sufficient (financial) resources for facilitating Art-Science collaborations and accompanying research. However, interdisciplinary Art-Science collaborations are shown to provide valuable, and progressive contributions to addressing complex problems, for instance complex climate topics as shown in *Collaborations for Future*. Hence, to create sustainable Art-Science collaborations accessible to explore, learn, create, and achieving external impact together better institutional and financial support is essential.

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Appendix

Table 3 Interview guide

Thematic category	Question
General experience & Learning outcomes	How would you <u>describe your experience</u> participating in the collaboration?
	In what ways, if any, has your participation in the design-science collaboration <u>influenced your professional or creative development</u> ? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have you developed any <u>new skills, approaches, or perspectives</u> as a result? - Has your <u>way of thinking</u> about your work or projects changed? - Did the collaboration lead to <u>opportunities</u> or projects that might not have happened otherwise?
	Have you <u>incorporated</u> any methods, skills, or insights from the collaboration into your current work? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If so, which ones, and in what context?
	Did the collaboration <u>change your perspective</u> on interdisciplinary work between science and design? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If so, in what ways?
Post-Collaboration Effects	Have you <u>maintained any connections</u> with participants from the collaboration? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If so, in what context?
	Has your experience in the collaboration played a role in <u>shaping any new projects</u> , research, or creative work? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If yes, how did it contribute to their development?
Evaluation & Assessment	How would you <u>define a 'successful'</u> design-science collaboration? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What <u>criteria</u> do you think should be used to evaluate its impact?
	Are there any other <u>valuable</u> aspects of Design-Science collaborations we haven't talked about?

Table 4 Ethical Considerations

Ethics Check	Description
Are you collecting data from individuals or groups of individuals (your target audience)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes? Continue filling out this table <input type="checkbox"/> No? You don't need Ethics Approval and can stop here
Are you collecting personal data for registration purposes or as data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Registration purposes <input type="checkbox"/> As data
Define your target audience	Number of participants: 4-6 participants Characteristics (think about specific vulnerable groups, e.g. health related conditions, specific socio-economic conditions): Participants of the <i>Collaborations for Future Project 2024</i>
Describe your research method	<input type="checkbox"/> Content Analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Survey <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Interview <input type="checkbox"/> Focus group <input type="checkbox"/> Observation <input type="checkbox"/> Other, namely: Elaborate (max 3 sentences)
Describe the personal data that you will collect	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Name <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Surname <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Email address <input type="checkbox"/> Age <input type="checkbox"/> Gender <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Occupation <input type="checkbox"/> Four numbers of postal code <input type="checkbox"/> Other, namely: Elaborate (max 3 sentences):
	Other (non-personal) data:
Informed consent form is added to the proposal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes

Table 5 Codebook

Theme	Category	Definition
Social learning outcome	Relational learning	Participants learn through the social aspect of the collaboration and the collaboration process (Baird et al., 2014); They use or develop traits they rely on when collaborating; e.g. understanding of others' mindsets, communication, the building of relationships, trust, and cooperation) (Den Haan et al., 2018; Gallois et al., 2024)
	Learning on an emotional level (normative learning)	Participants learn through experiencing a change of viewpoints, a shift in values, a paradigm shift, or a convergence of group opinions (Baird et al., 2014) (learning outcomes on an emotional level, including reflection processes, or gaining self-knowledge or motivation through collaboration (Gallois et al., 2024))
	Cognitive learning	Participants learn through experiencing the acquisition of new knowledge or the restructuring of existing knowledge (Baird et al., 2014) (new perspectives, possibilities, and ideas for their personal or professional journey)
Post-collaboration outcome	Continuation of collaborative project or making use of the outcome	The participants work together beyond the official project timeline or utilize the outcomes of the collaboration.
	Future work and collaborations	The participants' future work or working environment was influenced by the collaboration by opening up the possibility of future collaboration.
Success of Design-Science Collaborations (Note: only apply to the last two questions of the interview guide regarding the participant's perspective on a successful collaboration)	Communication and outreach of the product	Participants justify the success of a collaboration through the fact that the collaboration (and its result) reaches out, informs about, and communicates the message of the collaboration to an audience.
	Sustainability & Long-term engagement	Participants justify the success of a collaboration through the maintenance of the collaboration and engagement beyond the official project timeline as a measurement of success
	Collaboration dynamics	Participants justify the success of the collaboration through the collaborative process including the personal and professional team dynamics (interaction, communication, teamwork, and commitment)
	Individual growth	The participants justify the success of the collaboration with the personal or professional growth they have observed in themselves

Challenges	Engagement & Team Dynamics	Participants experience challenges due to the different roles or efforts they invest in working together to contribute to the outcome, as well as different expectations of commitment and team dynamics within and between groups.
	Maintenance and Sustainability	The participants are faced with the challenge of maintaining the result and commitment of the collaboration after the project has been completed
	Facilitation	Participants experience challenges due to the structure of facilitating collaboration (e.g. workshop design or support)
	Impact	Participants face challenges related to the potential impact of the collaboration on the participants, the audience, or even society
	Understanding	Participants face challenges related to understanding the other discipline

The supplementary material consists of the following documents:

1. interview transcripts
2. form of consent signed
3. form of consent raw
4. Excel sheet (codebook, coded quotations, results)
5. R code for the graphics

